

Research Article

Facile Preparation of g-C₃N₄-WO₃ Composite Gas Sensing Materials with Enhanced Gas Sensing Selectivity to Acetone

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In this paper, g-C₃N₄-WO₃ composite materials were prepared by hydrothermal processing. The composites were characterized by means of X-ray powder diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), and N₂ adsorption-desorption, respectively. The gas sensing properties of the composites were investigated. The results indicated that the addition of appropriate amount of g-C₃N₄ to WO₃ could improve the response and selectivity to acetone. The sensor based on 2 wt% g-C₃N₄-WO₃ composite showed the best gas sensing performances. When operating at optimum temperature of 310°C, the responses to 1000 ppm and 0.5 ppm acetone were 58.2 and 1.6, respectively, and the ratio of the $S_{1000 \text{ ppm acetone}}$ to $S_{1000 \text{ ppm ethanol}}$ reached 3.7.

1. Introduction

Graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄) nanomaterial exhibits a stable layered structure and π -conjugated s-triazine unit composed of sp² hybridized carbon atoms and sp² hybridized nitrogen atom. g-C₃N₄ nanosheets have attracted the attention of researchers in recent years for its peculiar properties as a semiconductor such as immense specific surface area [1]. Wang et al. [2] prepared g-C₃N₄ by thermal treatment of glucose and urea, and the p-type sensor based on g-C₃N₄ exhibited good response to NO₂ at room temperature.

As a gas sensing material, WO₃ has been paid much attention in the past decade. Cho et al. [3] used ultrasonic spray pyrolysis to prepare WO₃ hollow spheres using a citric acid-containing precursor solution; the WO₃ hollow spheres exhibited a high response and good gas sensing selectivity to trimethylamine, but the sensor exhibited a depressed response to NO₂. Kida et al. [4] used acidification of Na₂WO₄ with H₂SO₄ solution to prepare lamellar-structured WO₃

particles which had a high response ($S = 150\text{--}280$) even to dilute NO₂ (50–1000 ppb) in air at 200°C. A study by Ma et al. [5] showed that WO₃ nanoplates obtained through a topochemical transformation of the corresponding H₂WO₄ precursor exhibited high response to ethanol while operating at 300°C.

The photocatalytic activity of g-C₃N₄-WO₃ nanocomposites also has been reported by many researchers [6–9]; the photocatalytic performances of WO₃/g-C₃N₄ nanocomposites were higher than those of pure WO₃ and pure g-C₃N₄, which were attributed to the synergistic effect of WO₃ and pure g-C₃N₄. A study by Zhang et al. [10] showed that the ethanol sensing performance of α -Fe₂O₃/g-C₃N₄ nanocomposites was better than that of pure α -Fe₂O₃ and g-C₃N₄, which could be caused by porous α -Fe₂O₃ nanotubes wrapped by lamellar g-C₃N₄ nanostructures resulting in the formation of heterojunction. Cao et al. [11] reported that the gas sensing response and selectivity to ethanol could also be enhanced by modification of g-C₃N₄ nanosheets. The

combination of WO_3 and $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ may exhibit good gas sensing properties, which to the best of our knowledge has not been reported to date.

In this paper, we report the preparation of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ - WO_3 nanocomposites through a hydrothermal method and the investigation of their gas sensing properties. Analysis showed that 2 wt% $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ - WO_3 nanocomposite responded highly and selectively to acetone.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Material Preparation and Characterization. $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ was prepared by heating 2.0 g melamine in an oven at 520°C for 5 hours, while keeping the heating rate at $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, which was similar to that reported in the literature [12]. After cooling to room temperature naturally, the product was purified with ethanol, following which it was dried at 60°C for 24 h succeeded by milling.

For preparing the nanocomposites, a certain amount of as-prepared $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ was added to 40 mL deionized water and sonicated for 1 hour to obtain a $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ suspension. 0.0025 mol $\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was dissolved in 20 mL deionized water, and 4 mL concentrated hydrochloric acid was added dropwise in the Na_2WO_4 solution slowly while stirring resulting in the formation of H_2WO_4 ; the $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ suspension was added slowly to H_2WO_4 while stirring. The mixture was sealed in a 100 mL Teflon-lined stainless steel autoclave and heated at 200°C for 24 h; the obtained precipitate was filtered and washed with distilled water and ethanol, followed by drying in air at 80°C for 24 hours; finally, the $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ - WO_3 composite was obtained. The weight ratios of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ powders/ WO_3 (the weight of WO_3 was calculated according to the weight of $\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were 0 wt%, 1 wt%, 2 wt%, 3 wt%, and 4 wt% (the samples were labeled as S-0, S-1, S-2, S-3, and S-4, respectively).

X-ray diffraction (XRD, Bruker D8 Advance, $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation: $\lambda = 0.15418$ nm), operating at 40 kV and 30 mA in a 2θ range from 10° to 70° at room temperature, was used to analyze the crystal structure of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ - WO_3 nanocomposites. A scanning electron microscope (SEM, Hitachi S-4800 microscope), with an accelerating voltage of 10 kV, was used to characterize the surface morphology of the samples. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR, Nicolet 6700 FTIR Spectrometer) spectra were recorded by the KBr pellet technique in the range 400 – 4000 cm^{-1} . The chemical species of elements were analyzed by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, Thermo ESCALAB250Xi) with all of the binding energies corrected according to contaminant carbon ($\text{C}1s = 284.6$ eV). The specific surface areas were characterized by the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET, ASAP2010C) method using N_2 adsorption-desorption measurement.

2.2. Gas Sensing Measurement. The sensor device preparation process and the gas sensing measurement have been explained in the previous work [13]. The gas sensing response of the gas sensor was defined through the ratio of the resistance of the gas sensor in air (R_a) to that in the test gases (R_g). Figure S1, representing the gas sensor, is shown in supplementary materials.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Characterization. Figure 1 shows the XRD patterns of pure $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$, $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ - WO_3 (S-1, S-2, S-3, and S-4), and WO_3 . Two significant diffraction peaks were observed at 13.23° and 27.86° in the XRD pattern of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$, indicating the (100) and (002) planes of layered $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$; the weaker peak at 13.23° indicates the in-planar tris-s-triazine structural packing, and the stronger peak at 27.86° corresponds to the stacked of the aromatic systems between layers [6–8, 14]. All the diffraction peaks observed in XRD patterns of S-0, S-1, S-2, S-3, and S-4 could be indexed to the standard data of WO_3 (JCPDS 43-1035). The diffraction peaks of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ could not be found because of the low concentration of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ in the composites [14]. It was reported that the diffraction peaks of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ did not appear in the XRD patterns of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ - WO_3 composites when the content of WO_3 was higher than 10 wt% [15]. The average crystallite sizes were calculated by the Scherrer formula:

$$D = \frac{K\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta}, \quad (1)$$

where D is the crystallite size, K is the instrument correction factor, γ is the $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ wavelength (0.151418 nm), β is the full width at half maximum of the peaks, and θ is the position of the peaks. The average crystallite sizes of WO_3 in S-0, S-1, S-2, S-3, and S-4 were 54.9, 62.6, 44.4, 44.3, and 50.2 nm, respectively. The calculated particle size of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ was about 5.7 nm.

Figure 2 exhibits the SEM images of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$, pure WO_3 (S-0), and $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ - WO_3 (S-2). The morphology of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ was a sheet that consisted of small particles, and the particle sizes were about 200 nm. The WO_3 particle sizes in WO_3 and $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ - WO_3 were between 100 and 400 nm; the addition of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ in the composite had no obvious influence on the particle size of WO_3 . The particle sizes obtained from SEM images were larger than those calculated from the Scherrer formula, which manifested that the particles observed by SEM in $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$, pure WO_3 , and $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ - WO_3 were aggregates of smaller particles.

The FTIR spectra of WO_3 and $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ - WO_3 (S-2) are shown in Figure 3. The absorption peaks at 763, 822, and 935 cm^{-1} in the spectra of two samples originated from stretching vibrations of O-W-O in WO_3 [9, 15, 16]; the peaks at 1632 and 3436 cm^{-1} in the FTIR spectra of WO_3 and $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ - WO_3 (S-2) resulted from the vibration of bended H-O-H and stretched O-H of absorbed H_2O on the material surface [17]; and absorption peaks in the FTIR spectrum of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ - WO_3 (S-2), other than those of WO_3 , at 1244, 1321, 1411, 1567, and 1632 cm^{-1} were ascribed to stretching vibration of C-NH-C and C=N of heterocycles [15], which proved the existence of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ in the composite. The XPS results were discussed in the supplementary materials, which could prove the formation of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ - WO_3 .

3.2. Gas Sensing Characterization. The gas sensing responses of pure WO_3 , S-1, S-2, S-3, and S-4 to 1000 ppm concentration of acetone at different operating temperatures are shown

FIGURE 1: The XRD patterns of pure $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$, $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4\text{-WO}_3$ (S-1, S-2, S-3, and S-4), and WO_3 .

FIGURE 2: The SEM images of (a) $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$, (b) pure WO_3 (S-0), and (c) $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4\text{-WO}_3$ (S-2).

in Figure 4. An increase in the response with an increase in the amount of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ in the $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4\text{-WO}_3$ composite was observed while the content of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ was lower than 2 wt%; when the contents of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ in the $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4\text{-WO}_3$ composite were 3 wt% and 4 wt%, the responses decreased significantly; the optimal operating temperatures for S-1 and S-2 were all 310°C , which were better than that for pure WO_3 . The responses of pure WO_3 , S-1, S-2, S-3, and S-4 to 1000 ppm acetone at 310°C were 3.7, 16.2, 58.2, 1.0, and 1.3, respectively. It has been reported that pure $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$

exhibited very little response to acetone; the response improved significantly for a particular content of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ in a series of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4\text{-SnO}_2$ nanocomposites [18]. The response of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3/g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ to ethanol was also reported [11]; an appropriate amount of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ in the composites was propitious to the dispersion of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ in the composites and the formation of better heterojunctions; the reasons for the enhancement of gas sensing response were attributed to the larger specific surface area, better permeability, and heterojunction. A sensor based on the S-2 composite

FIGURE 3: The FTIR spectra of WO_3 and $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4\text{-WO}_3$ (S-2).

FIGURE 4: The gas sensing responses of pure WO_3 , S-1, S-2, S-3, and S-4 to 1000 ppm acetone at different temperatures.

exhibited higher response to acetone compared with pure WO_3 . The N_2 adsorption-desorption results are shown in Figure S3 of supplementary materials; the average pore size difference between S-0 and S-2 was not obvious, and the gas diffusion rates in the inner sections of S-0 and S-2 were approximate; the enhancement of gas sensing response of S-2 was probably attributable to the larger specific surface area of S-2 and heterojunction. Many literatures have reported the acetone sensing mechanism

of WO_3 [19, 20], and the conductance of the WO_3 sensor is influenced by the changes in chemisorbed oxygen present on the surface of the gas sensing material; on exposure of a sensor to air, oxygen is adsorbed on the surface of WO_3 , which in turn captured electrons from the conduction band of WO_3 , resulting in the decrease in electron concentration in the conduction band; oxygen molecules changes into $\text{O}_2^-(\text{ads})$, $\text{O}^-(\text{ads})$, and $\text{O}^{2-}(\text{ads})$ with variation of temperature. When the sensor was placed in an acetone

FIGURE 5: The responses of an S-2-based sensor to 1000 ppm acetic acid, acetone, formaldehyde, ethanol, acetaldehyde, and ammonia at different operating temperatures.

FIGURE 6: The responses of sensors based on S-0 and S-2 to six kinds of gases (1000 ppm) at 310°C.

vapor atmosphere, acetone reacted with $O_{2(ads)}^-$, $O_{(ads)}^-$, and $O_{(ads)}^{2-}$, releasing the electrons captured by oxygen molecules to the conduction band of WO_3 and decreasing the resistance of the sensor. The reaction is as follows:

Figure 5 depicts the responses of an S-2-based sensor to 1000 ppm acetic acid, acetone, formaldehyde, ethanol, acetaldehyde, and ammonia at different temperatures. The optimal operating temperatures for formaldehyde, ethanol,

and acetaldehyde were 360°C, 240°C, and 360°C, respectively; the maximum responses for acetic acid, acetone, and ammonia all appeared at 310°C. At an operating temperature of 310°C, the responses to 1000 ppm acetic acid, acetone, formaldehyde, ethanol, acetaldehyde, and ammonia were 8.9, 58.2, 6.0, 15.4, 4.3, and 6.0, respectively; the S-2 sensor showed significant gas sensing selectivity to acetone, with the response ratio of $S_{1000 \text{ ppm acetone}}/S_{1000 \text{ ppm ethanol}}$ reaching 3.8.

Figure 6 shows the responses of S-0- and S-2-based sensors to six kinds of gases, while keeping the concentration

FIGURE 7: The response transients of the sensor based on the sample S-2 composite to acetone (1000 ppm, 500 ppm, 100 ppm, 10 ppm, 1 ppm, and 0.5 ppm) at 310°C.

FIGURE 8: The curve of gas sensing response versus time of the S-2 sensor.

1000 ppm, at 310°C. The responses of the S-2 sensor to acetaldehyde, ethanol, and formaldehyde were lower than those of the pure WO_3 sensor. But the responses of the S-2 sensor to ammonia, acetone, and acetic acid were higher than those of the pure WO_3 gas sensor; especially, the response of the S-2 sensor to acetone was 15 times that of the pure WO_3 gas sensor, proving the role of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ in improving the selectivity of the gas sensor.

The response time and recovery time were calculated using the formula defined in a previous literature [21]. The response curve transients of the sensor based on the sample S-2 composite to acetone (1000 ppm, 500 ppm, 100 ppm, 10 ppm, 1 ppm, and 0.5 ppm) at 310°C are shown in Figure 7. The responses to 1000 ppm, 500 ppm, 100 ppm, 10 ppm, 1 ppm, and 0.5 ppm acetone were 58.2, 36.6, 17.2, 3.0, 1.8, and 1.6, respectively; the detection limit of the

S-2 composite-based sensor to acetone was 0.5 ppm. The response times for 1000, 500, 100, 10, 1, and 0.5 ppm acetone were 53, 24, 10, 15, 7, and 5 s, respectively, while the recovery times for 1000, 500, 100, 10, 1, and 0.5 ppm acetone were 29, 25, 6, 7, 12, and 3 s, respectively. The acetone concentration in the breath varies from 0.3 to 0.9 ppm for healthy people, but the acetone concentration exceeds 1.8 ppm for diabetic patients [22]. The S-2 composite-based sensor had a response of 1.6 to 0.5 ppm acetone which meant that it has the potential for application in diabetes detection.

The gas sensor stability is a significant parameter for a gas sensor, and the curve of gas sensing response versus time of the S-2 composite-based sensor is shown in Figure 8. The gas sensing response decreased significantly in seven days and then achieved stability between the seventh and thirtieth days. The stability of the sensor can be improved further. The

TABLE 1: Comparison of acetone gas sensing properties with different acetone gas sensors.

Material	Operating temperature (°C)	Detection limit (ppm)	Response (R_a/R_g) (concentration)	Selectivity	Stability (days)	Reference
Au/ZnO	365	20	2923 (100 ppm)	1.8	90	[23]
MgFe _{2-x} Ce _x O ₄	700	100	1.91 (2000 ppm)	1.2	-	[24]
Co ₃ O ₄ NWS-HCSs	150	1	23 (200 ppm)	4.6	-	[25]
PrFeO ₃	180	10	141 (200 ppm)	2.8	75	[26]
Pt-Fe ₂ O ₃	139	0.2	25.7 (100 ppm)	2.9	15	[27]
Rh-doped SnO ₂	200	1	60.6 (50 ppm)	8.6	-	[28]
ZnFe ₂ O ₄	260	10	52.8 (100 ppm)	3.2	30	[29]
g-C ₃ N ₄ -WO ₃	310	0.5	58.2 (1000 ppm)	3.7	30	This work

“-” means no data available in the literature.

g-C₃N₄-WO₃ composite (S-2) has proven itself to be a potential candidate for application as an acetone sensor, if the stability of the sensor can be improved.

Table 1 compares the gas sensing properties of different acetone sensors. Overall, the g-C₃N₄-WO₃ acetone gas sensor showed good sensitivity to acetone and also had significant selectivity. Besides, the detection limit is as low as 0.5 ppm which is the second lowest in the listed acetone sensor.

4. Conclusions

It can be observed that the content of g-C₃N₄ in g-C₃N₄-WO₃ composites influences the response and selectivity of g-C₃N₄-WO₃ composite-based sensors to acetone. 2 wt% g-C₃N₄-WO₃ composite (S-2) showed the best gas sensing performances in the series of g-C₃N₄-WO₃ composites, when operating at an optimum temperature of 310°C; the responses to 1000 ppm and 0.5 ppm acetone were 58.2 and 1.6, respectively, with the ratio of the $S_{1000 \text{ ppm acetone}}$ to $S_{1000 \text{ ppm ethanol}}$ reaching 3.7; the S-2 composite-based sensor was able to detect acetone at concentrations as low as 0.5 ppm. The sensor took 5 s and 3 s to respond to 0.5 ppm acetone and to recover; the g-C₃N₄-WO₃ composite (S-2) has proven to be a potential candidate for application as an acetone sensor if the stability of the sensor can be improved.

Data Availability

The underlying data related to this manuscript is available on request.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Supplementary Materials

Figure S1: gas sensor used for characterizing gas sensing behavior of samples. Figure S2: XPS spectra of g-C₃N₄-WO₃ (S-2): (a) full spectrum. (b) C1s. (c) N1s. (d) O1s. (e)

W. Figure S3: (a) N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherm of WO₃. (b) Pore size distribution curve of WO₃. (c) N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherm of g-C₃N₄-WO₃ (S-2). (d) Pore size distribution curve of g-C₃N₄-WO₃ (S-2). (*Supplementary Materials*)

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